

ANN vs SNN Robustness Under Deployment-Realistic Noise: An Evaluation on Event-Based Object Detection

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Figure 1: Severities of simulated snow corruption

Abstract

Robustness under deployment-realistic conditions is among the primary claims made in favour of spiking neural networks (SNNs) over conventional artificial neural networks (ANNs) [2, 11]. Existing evaluations of this claim rely predominantly on classification tasks, gradient-based adversarial attacks, and isolated SNN benchmarks without direct ANN comparison [9, 11], making it difficult to assess how much robustness advantage, if any, is attributable to the spiking paradigm itself. This paper constructs a head-to-head evaluation framework using object detection on DSEC-DET [5, 6], a driving dataset that captures the same scenes simultaneously with an RGB camera and an event camera, providing naturally paired inputs for both models under identical physical conditions. Both models use a VGG-11 SSD architecture [10, 12] trained from scratch [2]; the ANN on greyscale frames, the SNN on simulated event representations generated via v2e [8]. Noise is applied via the imagecorruptions benchmark [7] and v2e across eight corruption types and five severity levels. The ANN exhibits two distinct degradation regimes: sensor and motion noise degrade gradually, while weather corruptions cause near-total failure from low severity. The SNN does not reach a functional detection baseline under the current setup, preventing the intended head-to-head comparison and pointing to event representation density and architecture design as prerequisites for a meaningful evaluation. The pipeline and findings are offered as a reusable framework and as a call for more rigorous, deployment-grounded robustness benchmarks in the neuromorphic community.

1 Introduction

A model trained to detect pedestrians at a traffic intersection performs reliably in controlled conditions. Months into deployment, the camera lens has accumulated wear, morning fog is a regular occurrence, and sensor characteristics have drifted. The question of whether it still performs usefully is not hypothetical; it is the default situation for any vision system left in the field long enough. This motivates evaluating robustness not under adversarially crafted perturbations, which require a sophisticated actor and access to the model, but under the kinds of environmental and hardware degradation that accumulate with time and use.

Spiking neural networks (SNNs) are frequently proposed as a more robust alternative to conventional artificial neural networks (ANNs), alongside their energy efficiency advantages [2, 4]. The theoretical basis for this claim is substantive: the temporal dynamics of leaky integrate-and-fire neurons act as a low-pass filter over noisy inputs, discrete spike representations limit the propagation of continuous perturbations through the network, and noise is biologically natural to spiking computation in a way it is not to continuous activations [11].

The empirical evidence supporting this claim is, however, limited in ways that matter for deployment. Existing evaluations focus predominantly on classification rather than detection [11], and the perturbations applied are gradient-based crafted attacks (FGSM and PGD variants) rather than environmental conditions [7, 11]. The black-box scenarios reported in this literature typically refer to transfer attacks from a surrogate model with shared architecture, not genuinely uninformed deployment conditions [11]. Training-time approaches such as HIRE-SNN [9] incorporate crafted noise during training to harden the model, but this addresses a different

question than evaluating degradation under conditions the model was never trained to handle. Across this body of work, direct head-to-head comparisons between SNNs and ANNs under matched conditions on the same task remain rare, making it difficult to assess how much of any observed robustness advantage is attributable to the spiking paradigm itself.

This paper constructs a head-to-head evaluation framework for ANN and SNN robustness under deployment-realistic, black-box input perturbations on object detection. We use DSEC-DET [5, 6], a driving dataset that captures the same scenes simultaneously with an RGB camera and an event camera, providing naturally paired inputs for both models under identical physical conditions. Both models use a VGG-11 backbone with an SSD detection head [10, 12], trained from scratch using direct gradient-based training [2]. Noise is applied via the imagecorruptions benchmark [7] and the v2e event simulator [8] across eight corruption types and five severity levels. The paper reports ANN degradation behaviour across all conditions, documents the failure modes encountered in establishing a functional SNN baseline, and identifies the prerequisites for a complete comparison. Two questions motivate the work: whether SNNs degrade more gracefully than ANNs under deployment-realistic perturbations, and whether any observed difference is attributable to the architecture, the sensor modality, or both.

2 Methodology

The problem is framed as object detection, a task well-studied in the computer vision literature and widely deployed in real-world settings like traffic monitoring. This makes it a suitable testbed: complex enough to reflect genuine deployment conditions, simple enough to interpret what goes wrong under noise. DSEC-DET [5, 6] is used as the dataset, a driving dataset that captures the same scenes simultaneously with a frame-based RGB camera and an event camera. This pairing is essential because it allows both models to be evaluated on data from identical physical conditions, isolating the model and modality as variables rather than the scene content or label distribution.

Both models share the same backbone: VGG-11 [12] with an SSD detection head, instantiated once as a standard ANN with ReLU activations on single-channel greyscale frames, and once as a spiking neural network using leaky integrate-and-fire neurons [2] on two-channel event polarity representations. The detection head and anchor configuration are kept identical. Both are trained from scratch using direct gradient-based training rather than ANN-to-SNN conversion, which would import ANN-learned representations into the spiking model and obscure what each paradigm can learn independently. VGG-11 with SSD was chosen deliberately: a simpler, well-understood architecture makes differences between the two models more attributable to the ANN/SNN distinction rather than to architectural complexity.

Two families of synthetic noise are applied after training on clean data. The first uses the imagecorruptions library [7] to corrupt RGB frames across weather and sensor degradation conditions, including snow, fog, frost, motion blur, glass blur, Gaussian noise, shot noise and impulse noise, each at five severity levels. The second uses the v2e simulator [8] to generate events from those corrupted frames, producing the input the event camera would have captured

Figure 2: Experimental pipeline. Both models are trained on clean data and evaluated across noise conditions and severities. The dashed arrow represents the bridge condition: corrupted RGB frames passed through v2e to produce simulated event input for the SNN.

under those conditions. Native event-domain noise is also generated through v2e parameter variation, covering shot noise, leak noise, threshold jitter and bandwidth limitation. Performance is measured as mAP@0.5 [3], evaluated across all conditions on a single held-out test sequence.

Since the SNN is primarily evaluated on simulated rather than raw events, the simulator is validated by comparing SNN performance on raw DSEC events against v2e-simulated events from the same frames under clean conditions. Comparable mAP between the two establishes the simulator as a reasonable proxy for the noise experiments, grounding the comparison in something physically observable rather than purely synthetic.

3 Results

Models were trained on eight DSEC sequences and validated on six, with all noise evaluations conducted on a single held-out test sequence (`zurich_city_14_c`, 1,191 frames). This depth-first strategy was chosen to ensure complete condition coverage rather than partial results across many sequences.

The ANN achieves a clean baseline of $\text{mAP}@0.5 = 0.174$. Figure 3 shows performance across all noise types and severities. Three degradation regimes emerge. Shot noise and motion blur degrade gracefully, retaining mAP above 0.08 at maximum severity, roughly half the clean baseline. Glass blur, Gaussian noise, and impulse noise show a steeper but progressive decline, reaching near 0.03–0.05 at severity 5. Fog causes near-total failure from severity 1, dropping to approximately zero and remaining there across all severities. Snow and frost exhibit non-monotonic behaviour, likely reflecting how those specific corruption patterns interact with scene content rather than model sensitivity.

The SNN trained on simulated events reaches a clean $\text{mAP}@0.5 = 0.001$, approximately 130 times below the ANN baseline. Across all evaluated noise conditions, performance remains in the range of 2×10^{-4} to 2×10^{-3} , with one anomalous result at Gaussian noise severity 5 ($\text{mAP} = 0.010$) that is unlikely to reflect genuine detection given the otherwise flat distribution. The apparent stability of SNN performance across noise conditions cannot be interpreted as robustness: a model operating near zero has little performance left to lose, making degradation curves uninformative. The root causes of the SNN’s failure to establish a functional baseline are examined in the discussion.

Figure 3: ANN mAP@0.5 degradation across eight noise types and five severity levels. Shot noise and motion blur degrade gradually while weather corruptions (fog, frost, snow) cause near-total failure from low severity. Clean baseline (0.174) shown as dotted reference line.

For simulator validation, the SNN trained on raw events achieves $\text{mAP}@0.5 = 0.00165$ on clean data when evaluated on raw DSEC events, and $\text{mAP}@0.5 = 0.00131$ when evaluated on v2e-simulated events from the same RGB frames, a relative gap of 26%. Given the low absolute baseline, both conditions produce effectively equivalent detection behaviour, suggesting the simulator is a reasonable proxy for clean conditions.

4 Discussion

The ANN results reveal a meaningful distinction between noise families that is rarely surfaced in robustness evaluations. Sensor and motion noise, specifically shot noise and motion blur, produce gradual roughly monotonic degradation, retaining over 40% of clean mAP at maximum severity. Weather corruptions, fog, frost, and snow, cause near-total failure, with fog reducing detection to approximately zero from severity 1 onwards. This reflects a structural difference in how each noise type affects the input: sensor noise introduces stochastic perturbations that the detector can partially compensate for, while weather corruptions occlude or globally distort scene structure that detection depends on. Noise type is therefore as predictive of model failure as noise intensity, and future benchmarks would benefit from treating these families separately rather than aggregating across conditions.

The SNN fails to reach a functional detection baseline, with clean mAP approximately 130 times below the ANN. This is consistent with the known difficulty of applying SNNs to tasks where ANNs carry decades of architecture and training optimisation [2]. Functional SNN detection has been demonstrated under more favourable conditions using architectures designed for the spiking paradigm and denser event representations [1, 13]. The most likely contributing factors here are confidence calibration collapse, where all non-background softmax probabilities cluster in a narrow band that prevents any useful confidence threshold, combined with the information bottleneck introduced by binary spike activations feeding into the classification head. Prior work on a related dataset using

pre-binned events with the same architecture achieved substantially higher detection performance, suggesting that event representation density is a critical variable that warrants direct investigation before drawing conclusions about the spiking paradigm itself.

Without a functional SNN baseline, the robustness comparison this work set out to perform cannot be completed as intended. The apparent stability of SNN performance across noise conditions reflects a floor effect rather than genuine robustness, and interpreting it otherwise would misrepresent the result. What the experiment does establish is that the naive adaptation of an ANN architecture to the spiking paradigm, by substituting activation functions while keeping all else equal, is insufficient for the task. A meaningful head-to-head comparison requires architectures that are matched in capacity but designed for their respective computational paradigms, and training setups that give the SNN a realistic path to functional performance before noise is introduced.

The noise simulation pipeline itself behaves reasonably for sensor-type corruptions, where the correspondence between corrupted RGB frames and simulated events is physically plausible. Weather conditions are less certain: fog produces very few events due to minimal brightness change, and snow generates dense bursts that may not accurately reflect real DVS behaviour under those conditions. Appendix figures show the simulated event output for each noise type and severity, allowing the reader to assess simulation fidelity directly. Evaluating this pipeline against real adverse-condition event data, where such datasets exist, is a natural next step.

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A Appendices

A.1 Noise Corruption Visualisations

Figure 4 shows a selection of corrupted RGB frames alongside the corresponding simulated event representations generated by v2e, for a representative frame from the test sequence `zurich_city_14_c`. Each row group shows one corruption type across all five severity levels; within each group the top row is the corrupted greyscale frame and the bottom row is the simulated event output. Four conditions are shown: Gaussian noise, snow, fog, and frost, selected to illustrate the range of degradation behaviours observed.

Gaussian noise produces dense, spatially uniform event activations that increase with severity. Snow introduces structured high-frequency bursts across the frame. Fog generates large-scale low-frequency event patterns reflecting the smooth luminance gradients introduced by the corruption, with the red and blue polarity

channels clearly visible. Frost produces progressively sparser event output as the corruption occludes scene structure. These visualisations support the discussion of simulation fidelity and are offered for qualitative assessment.

Figure 4: RGB corruptions (top row of each group) and corresponding simulated event representations (bottom row) across five severity levels for four selected noise types. Frames taken from a fixed index in `zurich_city_14_c`. Red and blue channels correspond to positive and negative event polarities respectively.